

Effect Of Stress on Cattle Reproduction

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Abstract

Stress has been reported to influence the animal reproduction adversely. The impact of stress on reproduction depends on the type of stress, genetic predisposition of the animals, timing and duration of the stress. It inhibits GnRH/gonadotropin secretion in hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis through secretion of Adrenocorticotropin (ACTH), glucocorticoids (GH) and catecholamine (CA). With a better understanding of the basic biology and altered physiological processes involved in stress adaptability, it would be possible to devise strategies for animal welfare and optimal production.

Introduction

The inability of an animal to adapt to its environment is a sign of stress, and this phenomenon is frequently represented in a failure to reach genetic potential, such as for growth rate, milk supply, disease resistance, or fertility. The impact of stress on reproduction depends on the type of stress, genetic predisposition of the animals, timing and duration of the stress. Reproductive processes like expression of sexual behavior, ovulation, and embryo implantation are controlled by neuroendocrine system. The alterations in neuroendocrine responses as a result of stress are likely to influence these processes.

Stress Neuroendocrinology

Adrenocorticotropin (ACTH), glucocorticoids (GH), and catecholamine (CA) the hormones that mammals release in response to environmental changes. The amount released depends on the type and severity of the stress that is present. LH release changes when there are elevated cortisol levels and associated depression. Increased levels of Prostaglandin F₂ alpha (PGF₂ alpha), ACTH, epinephrine and norepinephrine concentrations affect the reproduction badly. Stress factors activates the HPA axis and inhibits GnRH and LH via an HPA-dependent mechanism. Other stressors, such as postpartum negative energy balance, inhibit GnRH and LH production but do so via different

mechanisms than the HPA axis. It's impossible to completely avoid the stress that management causes. Stress must be kept to a minimum for the endocrine parts of the reproductive axis to work at their best, which will lead to the best reproductive success.

Types of Stress

1. Heat

The occurrence of heat stress is affected by a number of variables, including solar radiation, wind speed, air temperature, and humidity. An early reproductive response to heat stress is the decrease in the intensity of oestrus and consequently low fertility.

1.1 In the female

Sexual behavior and fertility rate are the main indicators of the mammalian female reproduction that are negatively affected by environmental stress.

1.1.1 On fertility

Heat stress can alter the ovarian steroidogenesis, follicular dynamics and lowers the follicular dominance in the next cycle. A temperature increases of 0.5°C uterine during hot days caused a decrease in the rate of fertilization. In cattle, heifer's exposure to 32°C for 72 hours after insemination, inhibit embryonic development, however, it is known that 48 % of the females held 21°C, can become pregnant without any problem. In summer, 80% of oestrus may be undetectable. It is reported that when the rectal temperature of the animals increased from 38.5°C to 40°C in 72 hours after insemination service, pregnancy rates can decrease up to 50%.

1.1.2 On embryos

Several studies have indicated that in cattle, embryonic development is highly sensitive to high temperatures, in the top three to 11 days after service; acquiring more heat tolerance as the gestation period progresses. It is well known that compared to embryos created naturally, those created by in vitro fertilization (IVF) are more vulnerable to heat stress. The greatest loss of bovine embryos from IVF, occur before 42 days, when females are under heat stress.

1.2 In the male

Environmental stress can cause low sperm quality, which is closely related to low fertility in females, probably due to a combination of low fertilization rates and increased embryonic mortality. The quality of the ejaculate is correlated with alterations in certain crucial stages of the spermatogenic cycle brought on by direct exposure of the testis to high temperatures.

2. Nutrition

In cattle, stress during transportation, has a detrimental effect on the physiology of the animal that the stress caused by lack of food and drink. In nutrition stressed females there is lighter Corpus

luteum, altered constituents of allantoic fluid and early embryonic mortality. In Heifers and cows, the drop in oocyte quality in the early postpartum period is associated with negative energy balance and low body condition of the animals, which is expressed in developing embryos increased and aberrant having embryos, resulting in loss of the warmest months of the year. A proactive factor could be the adequate food supply in quantity and quality, which have direct effects on reproduction and on the alterations caused by the indirect effects of nutritional stress

3. By handling

Repeated negative interactions by employees can lead to greater fear of humans in farm animals, which in turn through stress can compromise reproductive efficiency in these animals. The female reproductive system is affected by electrical bites, immobilization, and other stress management techniques. Numerous driving situations, such as over mobilizing inseminated females, using force to separate animals, mobilizing animals under management's control for different purposes, etc., can negatively affect an animal's ability to reproduce. The greater adverse effect of stress can be observed on onset and expression of oestrus behavior. The animal's temperament is very important in determining how much stress it experiences. In cattle, the *Bos indicus* have a more aggressive and nervous temperament than *Bos taurus*.

Management of Stress

For heat stress

The greatest ways to mitigate the consequences of heat stress are: 1) Environmental alteration through physical means, 2) Breeding races with lower heat stress sensitivity, and 3) Good nutritional management. Proper ventilation and water sprinklers to control body temperature, shadows and ceilings for solar radiation can reduce the heat stress on the animal to a greater extent. Animals with white fur are less sensitive to heat stress. Implementation of frozen embryos and insemination with frozen semen should be done in less hot time.

By handling

Provision of free and required area per animal for comfort, bathing females before service and 3 to 5 days, breeding in less hot periods, implementation of oestrus synchronization programs, to schedule inseminations or services could be helpful in reducing the ill effect of stress on reproduction. Females should not be isolated long before artificial insemination or service.

By feeding

Correctly balancing diets, giving the energy required to offset falling consumption, reducing intake of fibre and protein, and increasing energy can stop the decline in reproductive efficiency brought on by a negative energy balance.

Conclusions

It is impossible to avoid all of the stress-inducing circumstances because many of the environmental stressors mentioned above occur frequently. When an animal does not consider the circumstances to be stressful, stressors do not cause the HPA axis to become active. Therefore, steps must be taken to minimize the detrimental effects of and/or to fully acclimate cattle to these stressors. For homeostasis and maximum productivity in cattle, ideal climatic conditions, proper management techniques, and nutrition are essential. Innovative studies are required to understand the processes underlying the endocrine dysregulations brought on by environmental stresses. For effective animal production systems, health, and improved product quality, research is also needed on dietary regimens and the right ways to limit an animal's exposure to unfavorable climatic circumstances.

